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Experimental Characterization of *Grewia Mollis* Root Fibre Reinforced Polyethylene Terephthalate Matrix Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

The reinforcement of different polymers by natural fibres has recently been the center of attention among many research groups around the globe. The major factors that affect the mechanical performance for the composites are the surface treatments and the variation in the physiochemical properties for the reinforcing material. This study investigated the physiochemical and the mechanical properties of *Grewia mollis* root fibre reinforced polyethylene terephthalate matrix composite material/s. Experimental research design was adopted for the study. The traditional hand lay-up method was applied in producing the composites and their physiochemical properties represented by moisture and oil absorption alongside mechanical properties represented by compressive and tensile strengths were investigated according to ASTM standards. Descriptive statistics of percentage (%) scatter plot and bar charts were used to analyze and present the data. The result revealed that moisture absorption decreases while oil absorption increases as the concentration of NaOH increases and static with time. This implies that the untreated composites absorb more moisture than oil whereas the treated composites absorb more oil than moisture. The compressive and tensile strengths properties of the treated composites were improved significantly as the concentrations of NaOH increases up to a threshold point of 15% before experiencing a decrease from threshold points of 20-25%. This shows that composites treated with 10–15% NaOH gave better improvements than 20–25% and the maximum improvements were found for 15% NaOH. Therefore, on the basis of % NaOH, threshold point of 15% possessed the ideal combination of physiochemical and mechanical properties. The outcome of the study showed that the treated composites might be used as an alternative to other naturally fiber-based product since they offered better physiochemical and mechanical properties than the untreated composites. According to the study, appropriately adjusting these processing parameters may result in a more effective or practical composites solution for our domestic and industrial applications.

Keywords: *Grewia mollis* fibre, Reinforcement, Polyethylene terephthalate, Composite, Characterization

1.0 INTRODUCTION

These days, a lot of researchers are working in the field of polymer composites containing natural fibres to develop either fully or partially biodegradable green composite due to increasing concerns about the environment. There has been increased interest in the development of composite materials with relevant physicochemical, chemical and mechanical properties for use in domestic and industrial applications in the last two decades. This development has impacted life and the nature of jobs in all fields of science and technology. Polymer science and technology as the main vehicle for human resources development needs to heed to the constant development of natural fibre-reinforced polymer composites. When compared to synthetic fibers, natural fibers are thought to be among the more beneficial to the environment because of their superior qualities¹. Sustainability and eco-friendliness are the main current criteria for manufacturing products². However, composite materials including naturally sourced fibres, therefore, are suitable to fulfilling the green requirements for producing eco-friendly products with interesting physicochemical and mechanical properties^{3,4}.

Alas, the non-biodegradability and high cost of commonly used composite materials, such as glass and carbon-reinforced polymeric material, limit their sustainability^{2,5}. Given these limitations, low-cost natural fibres have been introduced as alternative to the existing synthetic fibres in composite material formulation because they have sufficient mechanical qualities, are low in density, and are well biodegradable². Polymer engineering is becoming the way of life in this increasingly global economy due to rapid development in the usage of low-cost natural fibres in composite⁶. This constant development requires the current regeneration of polymer scientists to wide their searches, skills and to be fully prepared to face the tasks in the world of polymer engineering and technology.

The problem faced by manufacturers is the selection of natural fibre which is the most important process for polymer composites with comparable or better physicochemical, mechanical, and other functional properties⁷. Several studies on the composites made from polyethylene terephthalate matrix and natural fibres such as groundnut husk, wood dust particles, and tea leaves waste fibres were reported in the literature. *Grewia mollis* fibre (GMF) has been reported to be utilized in composites, majorly because of its availability and cost efficiency⁶. In the current study, its root fibre was selected as reinforcement material for polyethylene terephthalate composite formulation.

This research aimed at extracting cellulose fibre from *Grewia mollis* root (GMR) and developing composite materials from the extracted *Grewia mollis* root fibre (GMRF) and waste polyethylene terephthalate (FARO water bottles) with the view to reducing waste disposal in our environment and to reveal the trend of alkali treatment on the physicochemical and mechanical properties of the produced composite materials and justifies their optimum alkali treatment. The identification of these physicochemical, mechanical and other features of the created composite materials is paramount important, which if appropriate would be suggested for use in domestic and other related industrial applications.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials:

The used FARO water bottles were gathered from different parts of Yola, which is a city in Adamawa State, Nigeria, located at latitude 9.280 and longitude 12.480. GMRF was used as reinforcement material which was collected from Bagale Mountain located at Girie Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

2.2 Methods:

2.2.1 Sample Preparation

The waste bottles were cut into smaller pieces to foster the dissolution in solvent (Figure-1). The GMRF was extracted and chemically processed by retting, scouring, bleaching, and mercerizing processes respectively (Figure-2). These were done according to the standard methods adopted by John, Usman and Usman *et al.* ^{6,8,9}. The retting process involved the subjection of the fibre with 5% NaOH for 4hours; this was followed by scouring which involved treatment of the fibre with 2% sodium hydroxide to remove all impurities by oxidation. The fibre becomes cleaner, stronger, and more absorbent. The fibre was bleached

with 5% hydrogen peroxide at 100°C for 1 hour in the water bath, to remove all-natural colouring matter by oxidation. The fibre was then mercerized with 5-25% sodium hydroxide to justify the optimum alkali treatment for the composite and dried under the sun, natural air and oven to remove the free water and later stored in an air tight container after cutting into smaller pieces. By melting phenol in an oil bath at 45°C, the solvent for dissolving polyethylene terephthalate (PET) was prepared and mixing it with liquid 1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane in the ratio 60/40 w/w as described by John, Usman, Dass and Usman *et al.* ^{6,8-10}.

Figure-1: Pulverized PET particles.

Figure-2: Grewia mollis root fibre.

2.2.2 Preparation of Waste PET Solution

In a beaker filled with phenol-1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane solution, the crushed polyethylene terephthalate (Figure-1) was added and heated to 100°C. The mixture was agitated until the entire PET was dissolved, producing a thick liquid as reported by John, Usman and Usman *et al.* ^{6,8,9}.

2.2.3 Formulation of GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials

The composite panels were formulated using the standard procedure described and adopted by John, Usman and Usman *et al.* ^{6,8,9}. An aluminium mould was prepared and de-bonding substance was first introduced on the inner area of the mould followed by a pigmented gel coat to give high quality surface finish. 20g of the crushed fibre was manually laid in the mild randomly and the melted polyethylene terephthalate was poured and casted into the mould. The prepared composite materials were allowed to air dry to a structural panel for 1 hour at ambient temperature. They were then extracted from the mould, labeled and stored at room temperature in an open space in the laboratory for further use (Figure-3).

Figure-3: Formulated GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials.

2.2.4 Characterization of GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials:

2.2.4.1 Moisture Absorption Test (ASTM D355):

The composite materials were divided into 20x10x3 (length x width x thickness) mm³ pieces, and they were let to soak for up to 168 hours at 25°C in a stable water bath. Weighing the specimen both before and after it was submerged in moisture allowed us to calculate how much moisture it had absorbed. The equation provided by John, Usman and Usman *et al.* ^{6,8,9} was used to calculate the proportion of moisture that was absorbed as shown below:

$$\text{Absorption (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{initial weight} \times 100}{\text{Final weight}} \quad (1)$$

2.2.4.2 Oil Absorption Test (ASTM Oil No. 3):

The test employed using engine oil as medium, the standard testing method described by Munoz and Garcia-Manrique¹¹ and adopted by John, Usman and Usman *et al.*^{6,8,9} was employed. The composite specimens were cut into 20x10x3 (length x width x thickness) mm³ and immersed in a stable oil bath at 25°C for different time intervals (up to 168 hours). Weighing the specimen both before and after it was submerged in engine oil allowed us to calculate how much oil was absorbed. The same equation used for the moisture absorption test was utilized to determine the engine oil absorption percentage.

2.2.4.3 Compressive Strength Test (ASTM D695-97):

The test was performed according to ASTM D695-97 using an Enerpac Universal Hydraulic Digital Material Testing Machine (model: HUNG TA INSTRUMENT CO. LTD., Taiwan). The composite materials were cut into cuboid shapes with dimensions of thickness (t) of 3mm and width (b) of 15mm and placed on the machine and compressed. The compressive load was applied on the composite samples until failure occurs and the load was noted and recorded as well. The compressive stresses of the composite materials were determined using the formula as shown below:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{bxt} \tag{2}$$

Where: σ_c = compressive stress of the composite sample (MPa), p = load (N), b = width of the composite sample (mm), t = thickness of the composite sample (mm)¹².

2.2.4.4 Tensile Strength Test (ASTM D638-99):

The test was carried out in according with ASTM D638-99 using an Enerpac Universal Hydraulic Digital Material Testing Machine (model: H50KS-0404, Hounsfield Series S, UK) with a cross-head speed of 10mm/min and a span distance of 50mm. The composite samples were cut with dimensions of thickness (t) of 3mm and width (b) of 15mm and mounted on the machine and the tensile force were noted and recorded. The tensile stresses of the composite materials were determined using the formula below:

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{A} \tag{3}$$

Where: σ_t = Tensile stress of the composite sample (MPa), p = Applied load (N), A = Width * thickness of composite sample (mm)^{6,8,9}.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Effect of Moisture Absorption on GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials:

The effect of moisture absorption on GMRF reinforced PET matrix composite materials against time was studied. The properties of untreated GM fibre/polyester composites were obtained along with that of the treated ones. The result obtained shown that the absorption rate was very high at first 24 hours and steadily increased up to 96 hours. This gradual increase in moisture absorption could be as a result of low cross-linking density between the fibre and the matrix¹³. An apparent equilibrium was attained at 96–168 hours of soaking time as there was no significant variation in percentage absorption within these periods for both the untreated and the treated composites. The absorption rate for the treated composites was far lower than that of the untreated ones as depicted in Figure-4.

Figure-4: Effect of moisture absorption on GMRF reinforced PET matrix composite materials.

These observations agree with the investigations of Masoodi and Pillai and Usman^{12,14}. The higher absorption rate shown by the untreated polyethylene terephthalate composites could be due to the low compatibility of the hydrophobic polyethylene terephthalate matrix and the present of strongly polarized hydroxyl groups in natural fibre causing smooth interaction between the fibre and the moisture molecules. Thus, when subjected into moisture, it absorbed some volumes of moisture for first hours than the treated fibres, hence, resulting to a poor moisture resistance¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The lower absorption rate for the treated polyester composites could be due to excessive extraction of lignin content of the fibre as the concentration of NaOH increases progressively with time, which at higher concentration may result in damaging the ultimate cell walls of the fibre and subsequently reducing the absorption capacities of the fibre and thereby strengthening the interfacial bonding between the polymer matrix and the fibre, leading to a considerable improvements in the physiochemical and mechanical properties of the composites with higher concentration of sodium hydroxide^{6,8,9,12,15,19}. This also account for an extremely slow increase in absorption rate with time for both the composites treated with 20 and 25% NaOH. Therefore, the composite treated with 5% has the highest moisture absorption and the composite treated with 25% has the lowest. This demonstrates that when NaOH concentration rises, moisture absorption falls. This indicates that there is a direct relationship between the absorption rate and the NaOH content. According to reports, mercerization tends to reduce absorption of moisture¹⁵.

3.2 Effect of Oil Absorption on GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials:

The effect of engine oil uptake (%) for the untreated and the treated GMRF/PET composites up to 168 hours of soaking time was also studied. The absorption rate was low at first 24 hours and then it slightly increased till 72 hours. After 168 hours of soaking time, the absorption rate was same. An apparent equilibrium was attained at 96–168 hours of soaking time as there was no significant variation in percentage absorption within these periods for both the untreated and the treated composites as depicted in Figure-5.

Figure-5: Effect of oil absorption on GMRF reinforced PET matrix composite materials.

This shows that the composites reached their maximum saturation points at these periods. The percentage absorption increases progressively as the concentration of NaOH increases. This implies that treated composites absorb more oil than the untreated ones. This is because natural organic material from plants and fruits shows low oil absorption ability due to their oleophobicity properties²⁰⁻²². These observations agree with the work of^{6,9,23}. The absorption of moisture is higher than that of the engine oil as depicted in Figure-5. This is because the density of moisture is lighter than engine oil²⁴. For the untreated composites, there was an initial rapid increase in moisture absorption and initial slow increase in oil absorption. For the treated composites, there was a slow increase in moisture absorption and initial rapid increase in oil absorption which is directly proportional to the concentration of NaOH.

3.3 Effect of Compressive strength (CS) on GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials:

The effect of GMRF composites on the CS as the concentration of NaOH varies was studied. The result revealed that untreated composite gave poor CS with Compressive value of 43.02MPa compared to composites treated with 5–25% NaOH. This may be due to the fact that natural fibres are characterized by high moisture uptake and this phenomenon decreases the adhesive characteristics of fibre surface and weakens the interfacial bonding between the polymer matrix and the fibre thereby deteriorating the mechanical properties of the composites as reported by Al-Mosawi and Ali and Usman *et al.*^{6,15}.

This implies that high strength is observed in treated composites which increase as the concentration or percentage (%) of NaOH increases up to a threshold point of 15% and then experienced a decrease from 20–25% as observed in this work and as reported by Usman¹². This signifies that composites treated with 10–15% gave better results than those treated with 20–25% as depicted in Figure-6.

Figure-6: Compressive strength variation of GMRF reinforced PET matrix composite materials with concentration.

This shows that bonding between the fibre and the matrix was very low at higher percentage (%) above 15% NaOH resulting to subsequence decrease in the CS of the composite panels treated with 20-25% NaOH as observed in the current study and same was reported in the work of Usman¹². There is slight difference in the trend as 15% emerges as the best with compressive value of 67.50MPa compared to the rest treated fibre reinforced polyethylene terephthalate matrix with compressive values of (5%=47.20, 10%=63.20, 20%=53.40 and 25%=51.00) MPa respectively and therefore had the optimum set of mechanical properties. This result is in agreement with the report of El-Tayeb, Mylsamy and Rajendran and Usman^{12,25,26}. This could be due to the facts that alkali treatments remove the lignin and hemicellulose content of the fibre making it well bonded with the polymer and improvement seen in their interfacial bonding which gives necessary strength Rao and Reddy *et al.* and Usman^{12,27,28}.

3.4 Effect of Tensile strength (TS) on GMRF Reinforced PET Matrix Composite Materials:

The effect of GMRF composites on the TS as the concentration of NaOH varies was studied. The result showed that TS increases as the concentration or percentage (%) of NaOH increases up to a threshold point of 15% and then experienced a decrease from 20–25% as observed in this work and as reported by

Usman, John and Usman *et al.*^{6,8,9}. This implies that composites treated with 10–15% gave better results than those treated with 20–25% as depicted in Figure-7.

Figure-7: Tensile strength variation of GMRF reinforced PET matrix composite materials with concentration.

This is because at low (%), the GM fibre is highly compacted by the polyethylene terephthalate and there is little or no fibre touching one another and that higher (%), above 15% will damage its cell wall resulting in low bonding between the fibre and the matrix leading to subsequent reduction in the mechanical properties of the composite¹⁵. There is slight difference in the trend as 15% emerges as the best with tensile value of 44.05MPa compared to untreated fibre reinforced polyethylene terephthalate matrix with tensile value of 32.85MPa. Therefore, on the basis of % NaOH, threshold point of 15% had the optimum set of mechanical properties. This result agrees with the investigations of Akter, John, Usman and Usman *et al.*^{6,8,9,18}. This may be due to the fact that natural fibres are characterized by high moisture uptake and this phenomenon decreases the adhesive characteristics of fibre surface and weakens the interfacial bonding between the polymer matrix and the fibre thereby deteriorating the mechanical properties of the composites as reported by Al-Mosawi and Ali and Usman *et al.*^{6,15}.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The results obtained from the physiochemical and mechanical tests showed that the absorption of moisture is higher than that of the engine oil and that the untreated composites absorb more moisture while the treated ones absorb more oil. This proved that the density of moisture is lighter than engine oil and natural fibres are hydrophilic not oleophilic. The treated composites recorded higher compressive and tensile values than the untreated ones. This implies that the treated composites will be sensitive to a wide range of applications where high compressive and tensile strengths variations are required.

Addition of NaOH in the composites significantly improved the mechanical attributes of the composites and the optimum improvements were found at 15% for both compressive and tensile strength. This implies that the composites treated with higher concentration of NaOH present better resistance to moisture and show good mechanical properties than those treated with lower concentration of NaOH and that higher percentage of NaOH, above 15% will damage their cell wall and subsequently reducing their mechanical properties. All these variations in mechanical properties are due to differences in the chemical composition and moisture absorption capacity of the composites.

This finding clearly showed that the produced composites with optimum processing parameter present better physiochemical and mechanical properties and could be used as an alternative to other commercially used natural fibre products. This shows that the potential application of *Grewia mollis* fibre based composites in domestic and industry are going to increase in near future.

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